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TRIP family genes TRIP10, TRIP12 and TRIP13 function in senescence and senescence bypass through the shieldin complex and the anaphase promoting complex (APC).

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We describe here function of a family of genes identified by their ability to interact with the thyroid hormone receptor in the presence or absence of T3 thyroid hormone, *TRIP* genes, as a target of senescence and senescence bypass that function through interactions with *MAD2L2*, a component of the the shieldin complex, and influence over a central regulator of the cell cycle, the anaphase promoting complex (APC).

Results

We studied total transcription in two models of senescence in human cells in vitro to measure TRIP family modulation during senescence and senescence bypass associated with transformation.

Figure 1: TRIP13 is silenced or repressed and TRIP10 is activated in senescence.

GSE262932

n=___ young fibroblasts (cells isolated from children)

n=___ aged fibroblasts (cells isolated from elderly humans)

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
9319	7.85E-07	0.232	4.9391567	1.1480769	463.67	TRIP13	2172/	
9322	1.07E-03	0.203	-3.2717697	-0.6630894	1019.55	TRIP10	4446/17001	

Figure 2: TRIP13 and TRIP10 can both be silenced in senescence.

GSE119987

n=___ young HUVEC

n=___ senescent HUVEC (proliferative senescence)

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
202734_at	1.12E-02	3.15	-4.114461	4.12E-01	TRIP10	2610/	
204033_at	8.83E-03	3.29	-3.8650826	3.43	TRIP13	2362/22277	

Transcriptional repression of TRIP13 was a conserved feature of the senescence gene signature: in senescence associated with aging in humans (in fibroblasts from young and aged adults), and in a replicative senescence model in which age was not a confounding factor.

Figure 3 and Figure 4: TRIP10 is silenced in oncogene-induced senescence (OIS), but activated upon senescence bypass with KRas G12V.

GSE146479

KRas wildtype

n=3 human lung epithelial cells (AALE); control vector

n=3 human lung epithelial cells (AALE); wild-type KRas

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
7205	5.28E-05	0.1072	4.0428301	0.4334091	12459.07	TRIP6	2517/	
9322	1.05E-02	0.1218	2.5602617	0.3117551	10029.23	TRIP10	5829/	

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GSE146479
KRas G12V

n=3 human lung epithelial cells (AALE); control vector
n=3 human lung epithelial cells (AALE); KRas G12V

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
9322	6.98E-03	0.15	-2.697961	-0.4039451	14611.9	TRIP10	2502/	
7068	5.07E-06	0.191	4.562043	0.8697281	404.73	THRB	864/19959	

Figure 5: Both Ras and Raf mutant oncogenes influence TRIP activation or repression.

GSE116631
Braf V600E in colorectal cancer cells

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
9320	2.03 e-13	0.137	-7.347	-1.004	12001.21	TRIP12	346/17721	

Ectopic expression of BrafV600E was sufficient to activate TRIP12 *in vitro*.

Finally, we studied expression of TRIP family members in primary tumors of a human cancer type that features BrafV600E mutation, melanoma, comparing total transcription in normal skin and in melanoma tumor tissue.

GSE111445
n=6 control (normal skin)
n=16 tumor (human; melanoma)

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
201546_at	9.34e-06	-5.716226	3.615492	-0.58195247	TRIP12	702/54675	

Figure 6: MAD2L2 with TRIP13 connects the anaphase promoting complex and sheildin complex

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2 Proteomic analyses (protein-protein interaction studies) indicated TRIP13 interacts with a component of
3 the shieldin complex, MAD2L2; TRIP13 thus likely exerted influence over the cell cycle through the
4 anaphase promoting complex (APC) by interactions with MAD2L2 which itself directly interacted with
5 components of the APC (**Figure 6**).

6 **Discussion**

7 Together we found that TRIP13 down-regulation was a transcriptional feature of senescence in human
8 cells, in senescence associated with aging and in that associated with replicative senescence in vitro.
9 Expression of mutant KRas G12V oncogene (but not wild-type KRas) resulted in activation of TRIP10,
10 while expression of a second mutant oncogene known for its ability to exert senescence bypass during
11 transformation of benign nevus to a transformed melanoma tumor resulted in activation of a second TRIP
12 family member, TRIP12. TRIP12 activation was a defining transcriptional feature of human melanoma,
13 suggesting that TRIP12 activation was a direct transcriptional consequence of BrafV600E whose induction
14 contributed to senescence bypass during entry into transformation.

15 TRIP family genes were identified based on their ability to interact with the thyroid hormone receptor in the
16 presence (or, in some cases, in the absence) of T3 thyroid hormone. TRIP12 has several described
17 functions relevant to transformation and cancer biology; it could function with UBR5 to recruit or facilitate
18 accumulation of RNF168 at damaged DNA sites for ubiquitylation of the chromatin and 53bp1/BRCA1
19 signaling, which was hyper-activated by TRIP12 depletion, and a second study found similar contribution
20 of TRIP12 to DNA repair during telomere damage but only in uncapped telomeres, where it functioned
21 with UBE2D3 to regulate RNF168 accumulation at the damage site. A third study described TRIP12 as a
22 contributor to oxidative stress responses that utilize CULD3-KEAP1 for NRF2 degradation functioning
23 through ubiquitin chain elongation. TRIP13 also has a described function in DNA repair, described to
24 function by promoting disassembly of the shieldin complex following recruitment of Mad2L2 (Rev7),
25 through "remodeling" which resulted in disassociation of REV7 from SHLD3 through the TRIP13 AAA
26 ATPase domain. A related, DNA repair-associated function for TRIP13 in cell cycle control through
27 regulation of the anaphase promoting complex (APC) through its ability to promote disassembly of the
28 mitotic checkpoint complex (MCC) which supports genomic stability during chromosome segregation in
mitosis functioning with the spindle assembly checkpoint (SAC) at the kinetochore; MCC inactivation was
required for SAC inactivation, and these were a function that required TRIP13 interactions with the
C-terminal domain of MAD2.

18 The data here and the described functions of TRIP12 and TRIP13 together suggest an intrinsic link
19 between DNA damage and cell cycle progression in transformation (senescence), a process that TRIP
20 activation. We found TRIP12 activation resulting from transient oncogene (Braf V600E) expression in vitro
21 which was present at clinical presentation at high quantity in the primary tumors of humans with
22 melanoma; we did not evaluate whether TRIP12 was important for maintenance of transformation in
23 established tumors or in cancer cells with established transformation, which would suggest TRIP12,
24 through a DNA repair-associated function as a factor required for shieldin complex disassembly, regulates
25 the anaphase promoting complex (APC), a required event that licenses chromosome segregation at the
26 spindle during mitosis.